

PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE COORDINATION OF ANTI-CORRUPTION BODIES

Kuchkarov Shokhrukh Farrukhovich¹

¹Under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Student of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Turgunbaev Rustambek Yarkinovich²

²Under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Student of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7427125>

Annotation: the article analyzes existing problems and shortcomings in coordinating the anti-corruption activities of law enforcement agencies in the country and offers and recommendations for improving the law based on recommendations from international institutions.

Keywords: anti-corruption, anti-corruption agencies, anti-corruption agencies, anti-corruption law, anti-corruption monitoring.

Among the broader reforms that are taking place in our country, the regulation of judicial matters, as well as improving the efficiency of the activities of law enforcement agencies in the fight against corruption, the rights of citizens and reforms are being undertaken to improve the mechanisms for protecting the rights and interests of citizens, openness of the activities of governmental and administrative bodies, enhance the role of parliament, and improve the legal foundations of law enforcement and judicial bodies.

At the same time, addressing strategic tasks to further strengthen the country's economic growth, improve the well-being of the people and improve the investment environment in the country requires the adoption of new systematic measures to ensure the effective implementation of the state's anti-corruption policies, as well as to address the causes and conditions of corruption. Fighting corruption and eliminating its dangerous consequences has been the main task of every state and society(1). In this regard, the state carries out its tasks by organizing the activities of its law-organized bodies and developing relevant legislative acts on the fight against corruption. Law enforcement agencies are known to be formed to protect the legal system of the state and to perform key functions in the field of law enforcement.

In the fight against corruption, it is important for law enforcement agencies to act within the powers entrusted to them and to coordinate their activities in achieving certain effectiveness. Coordination is primarily about establishing relationships with legal instruments. In most cases, the authority of law enforcement agencies to coordinate the fight against corruption and other

crimes is exercised by the body authorized to oversee the law. Today, coordination of the activities of the bodies and organizations involved in the fight against corruption in Uzbekistan is carried out by the National Anti-Corruption Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional councils. In recent years, despite the achievements achieved in combating corruption in our country, we have not been able to get rid of the negative effects of this disease. Transparency International ranked Uzbekistan 140th in 180 countries in a 2021 ranking of the world's countries for corruption. In 2020, Uzbekistan was ranked 146th. Most of the corruption crimes in Uzbekistan are official crimes.

As society develops, the powers and functions of law-enforcement agencies in the country will also change and adapt to the politics of the state. A thorough study of the system of social and legal relationships that arises in the process of coordinating the anti-corruption activities of law enforcement agencies is required. In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of crime prevention and combating crime" [12], not only corruption, but all types of crimes the work forms and methods of the state bodies implementing the prevention and fight against crime do not fully meet the current requirements due to the insufficient use of information and communication technologies, the fact that the measures for the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime are not directed to a specific destination and they are not comprehensively approached, as well as the fact that there is no efficiency in determining the reasons and conditions for the systematic commission of violations and the development of measures to eliminate them, it is shown that it does not produce the expected results.

It was emphasized that the competent bodies do not show enough initiative, there is no proper level of inter-agency cooperation, and the mutual disproportion of the implemented measures. The main goal was to create an effective system of coordination of crime prevention and fight against crime, to introduce modern organizational and legal mechanisms for preventing and eliminating violations of the law.

With this decision developed in cooperation with the Anti-corruption Agency and the United Nations Development Program, a system for rating the effectiveness of anti-corruption efforts is being introduced.

In this case, the rating assessment is carried out based on indicators set in five directions:

- creation and implementation of mechanisms and legal frameworks for combating corruption in state organizations.
- implementation of measures to identify, assess and reduce corruption risks.
- the presence of actions of leaders of state organizations that show an intolerant attitude against corruption.
- employees' awareness of the internal procedures for combating corruption and implementation of measures to improve their knowledge and skills in this field.
- the effectiveness of promotional activities aimed at raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population in the relevant field or branch of the fight against corruption and forming an uncompromising attitude towards this evil.

The rating evaluation system will initially be implemented as an experiment in the activities of 26 state organizations that are implementing the anti-corruption management system in their activities, and from July 1, 2022, it will be introduced in the activities of all state organizations.

It is worth noting that the evaluation of the rating is organized through the electronic platform "E-Anticor.uz". This ensures complete objectivity and transparency in rating formation.

The participation of representatives of the civil society institute is also envisaged in the rating evaluation work. To verify the impartiality of the results of the rating evaluation, a group of experts will be formed, consisting of at least 30 percent representatives of civil society institutions, which will independently carry out the rating evaluation.

The effectiveness of anti-corruption efforts is evaluated on a scale from 0 to 100 points, and the effectiveness of the activity is divided into "good", "satisfactory" and "unsatisfactory" categories.

In this, the activity:

measures to publicize the positive experience of state organizations rated as "good" in fighting corruption are determined and implemented.

Recommendations will be made to state organizations rated as "satisfactory" to further improve their anti-corruption activities.

In state organizations rated as "unsatisfactory", a program of measures aimed at eliminating identified deficiencies in the fight against corruption and improving their activities in this direction will be developed, the reports of the relevant leaders on its implementation will be heard quarterly at the meetings of the National Council for the Fight against Corruption. The issue of applying disciplinary measures to the heads of state organizations whose efficiency in the

fight against corruption has been found to be "unsatisfactory" for two consecutive years will be considered. (2)

This national rating system serves to form a unified approach to fighting corruption in state bodies and organizations, increase the responsibility of leaders in this direction, and improve the country's position in relevant international ratings.

With the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 27.05.2019 No. 5729 "On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan", special measures on the development of measures aimed at increasing the effectiveness of activities in the field of anti-corruption a commission was created, (6) studying the activities of law enforcement agencies in the field of combating corruption was determined as one of the main tasks of the commission. Based on the analysis of the theoretical sources, legal documents and practice studied in the research, we believe that it is appropriate to consider the following in order to ensure the effectiveness of the coordination of the activities of the bodies carrying out anti-corruption activities:

In our opinion, "Coordinating the activities of the bodies that carry out anti-corruption activities" can be understood, firstly, "in relation to the state policy on fighting corruption, and secondly, as an activity related to the detection and prevention of corrupt crimes." Any coordination activity begins with the formation of legal bases. According to principle 3 of the 2012 "Jakarta Declaration on Basic Principles of Anti-Corruption Agencies" (Jakarta Principles), the state's anti-corruption coordination agency should be established based on appropriate and stable legal foundations, such as the Constitution or a special law. In particular, the Law of the Russian Federation "On coordination of activities of law enforcement agencies to combat crime" and the Republic of Kazakhstan "On the Coordinating Council of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the rule of law, legality and fight against crime" There are presidential decrees. The subjects, principles, forms, and main directions of coordination of activities of law enforcement agencies to combat crime and corruption are clearly regulated in the aforementioned legal documents of these countries. In Uzbekistan, we can see that the powers of law enforcement agencies participating in the coordination of activities to combat crime and violations are mainly organizational in nature.

It is necessary to use the opportunities of electronic management in coordination of anti-corruption activities. The results of coordination should not remain only with this body or anti-corruption bodies, it is advisable to inform

parliament or other structures protecting the interests of society, as well as citizens.

Corruption offenses are not always crimes. This causes several problems in practice. That is, in the process of identifying and exposing corruption-related offenses that lead to administrative liability, the law does not provide for the implementation of rapid-search activities by the operational units of law enforcement agencies. In our opinion, among the grounds for carrying out rapid-search activities specified in Article 15 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Rapid Search Activities", the third paragraph of Part 1 of this article is "related to an offense related to corruption It is appropriate to fill it with the sentences "administrative affairs".

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori, 12.01.2022 yildagi PQ-81-son
2. <https://anticorruption.uz/uz/item/2022/01/13/korrupsiyaga-qarshi-kurashish-ishlarining-samaradorligini-reyting-baholash-tizimi-joriy-etiladi>
3. Patrick Meagher. Anti-Corruption Agencies: A Review of Experience. Office of democracy and governance Anticorruption. (https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/Pnadm208.pdf)
4. Po'latov B.X. Jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashni amalga oshiradigan organlar tomonidan qonunlar ijro etilishi ustidan prokuror nazorati. O'quv qo'llanma. - T.: Toshkent tezkor bosmaxonasi, 2007. - 312 b.
5. URL..<https://www.acauthorities.org/news/principles-anti-corruption>
6. <https://lex.uz/docs/-1461329>

